

Performance of Nanosponge and Nanosheet Al- and Ga-MFI Zeolites in Catalytic Pyrolysis of Biomass and Plastics

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ABSTRACT

MFI zeolitic materials in the form of nanosponges (nSP) and nanosheets (nSH) have been synthesized incorporating Al and Ga into the framework. Characterization of the samples by Ar adsorption-desorption and FTIR/Pyridine indicates they present remarkable differences in terms of accessibility (external/mesopore surface area) and acidity (ratio between the concentration of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites). These materials have been investigated as catalysts in the pyrolysis of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and lignocellulose (oak wood). In spite of very different reaction conditions and operation modes, some common results have been observed when comparing the catalytic performance of the Al- and Ga-MFI samples in both reactions. Nanosponge zeolites show superior cracking and deoxygenation activity during the catalytic conversion of LDPE and wood oak, respectively. On the other hand, Ga-containing materials favor the occurrence of dehydrogenation reactions, due to their relatively high content of Lewis acid sites, followed by the enhanced production of aromatic hydrocarbons. In overall, the Ga-MFI-nSP sample exhibits remarkable catalytic properties due to a suitable combination of accessibility and acid properties, the latter arising from the Ga incorporation into the zeolite framework.

Introduction

Pyrolysis is a promising route for the production of fuels and value-added products from organic residues and wastes. During the pyrolysis process, the feedstock is thermally decomposed at temperatures between 350 and 600 °C in the absence of oxygen or air. It yields a range of products: liquid fractions, non-condensable gases, and char (solid). Pyrolysis has a very high flexibility in terms of raw materials since it can be applied to a diversity of feedstock with different origin and nature. In recent years, a great interest has emerged on the pyrolysis of lignocellulose residues and plastic wastes, alone or as mixtures.^{1,2}

In the presence of catalysts, biomass and plastics pyrolysis narrows the broad distribution of products typically obtained under thermal conditions, improving significantly the selectivity towards valuable products. A large variety of materials have been investigated in catalytic pyrolysis over the past two decades, such as activated carbons,³ ordered mesoporous MCM-41 materials,⁴ Ni/Al₂O₃,⁵ Red Mud,⁶ magnesium oxide,⁷ zinc oxide⁸ and zeolites.⁹ Among these, zeolites have attracted a great attention due to their crystallinity, adjustable acidity and remarkable stability.¹⁰

ZSM-5 zeolite (MFI type structure) is particularly interesting in catalytic pyrolysis processes due to its three-dimensional channel system with 10- ring openings, consisting of straight (5.3×5.6 Å) and sinusoidal (5.1×5.5 Å) channels with intersections.¹¹ During catalytic pyrolysis, the primary cracking products are selectively converted over this zeolite into aromatic hydrocarbons via a series of deoxygenation and aromatization reactions.¹² The unique size and shape of ZSM-5 micropores prevent the formation of larger aromatic hydrocarbons due to space constraints. However, the size of the micropores in ZSM-5 (about 0.55 nm) also hinders the diffusion and

transformation of bulky molecules during the catalytic pyrolysis of both biomass and plastics. Accordingly, the performance of ZSM-5 zeolite in catalytic pyrolysis of biomass or plastics still has vast potential for further improvement.

One solution to improve the catalytic behavior of ZSM-5 zeolite is to generate mesopores, which can reduce the length of the diffusional pathways and increase the share of external surface area, strongly enhancing the accessibility of active sites. Moreover, the secondary network of micro- and meso-pores of hierarchical zeolites can minimize pore blockage and deactivation by coke formation. One interesting strategy to synthesize zeolites with enhanced accessibility is by direct hydrothermal crystallization with bifunctional surfactants proposed by Ryoo and colleagues.¹³ In this way, nanosheet MFI with uni- or multilamellar structures was firstly synthesized using $C_{22}H_{45}-N^+(CH_3)_2-C_6H_{12}-N^+(CH_3)_2-C_6H_{13}$ as structure directing agent (SDA).¹⁴ Then, nanosponge MFI zeolite with a three-dimensional disordered network of MFI nanolayers was prepared by accelerating nanosheet MFI nucleation using bulk zeolite crystals as seeds.¹⁵

On the other hand, the yield of valuable compounds in the pyrolysis of biomass and plastics can be increased by tailoring the acid site strength of ZSM-5 by substitution of Al for other elements. In particular, Ga incorporation into ZSM-5 zeolite is well-known to increase its aromatization activity.¹⁶ Compared to Ga-containing ZSM-5 zeolites (Ga/ZSM-5) prepared by impregnation, ion exchange or chemical vapor deposition methods, incorporation of Ga into the zeolite framework during the zeolite crystallization (Ga-MFI) avoids the formation of Ga oxides and allows the in situ creation of well-defined active centres.¹⁷ Brønsted acid sites in Ga-ZSM-5 zeolites possess a lower acid strength compared to conventional aluminosilicate ZSM-5,¹⁸ which can potentially suppress side reactions, avoiding coke formation and favoring the transformation of alkanes into olefins and consecutively into aromatic hydrocarbons.

A number of works has been earlier reported about the use of Ga-containing ZSM-5 as catalyst in plastics cracking or lignocellulose pyrolysis processes.¹⁹⁻²⁵ In most of them, Gallium is incorporated by impregnation or ion exchange over the ZSM-5 support generating mainly Ga₂O₃ after calcination. In contrast, just two works have been found investigating the behavior of Ga incorporated as framework heteroatom in the MFI structure in the catalytic co-pyrolysis of biomass and plastics²¹ and in the catalytic degradation of LDPE²⁶, respectively. Likewise, the catalytic applications of framework Ga-containing zeolites, possessing hierarchical porosity, have been little investigated, being mainly focused on ethane/propane dehydrogenation or methanol conversion into hydrocarbons.²⁷⁻²⁹

In this context, the main goal of this study is to assess the potential of MFI zeolites in the form of nanosheets (nSH) and nanosponges (nSP) as catalysts for the pyrolysis of plastics (low-density polyethylene, LDPE) and biomass (oak wood) and to compare their behavior depending on whether Al or Ga atoms are incorporated into framework positions. As far as we know, this is the first work disclosing the catalytic properties of Ga-MFI nanosheets and nanosponges in polyolefinic plastics cracking and lignocellulose pyrolysis. Both are scientifically and industrially interesting processes that present common aspects, like the occurrence of cracking reactions of bulky molecules and the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons, but also important differences, mainly related with the huge number and diversity of oxygenated components formed by biomass pyrolysis, which requires deoxygenation reactions to take place in a great extension to produce upgraded bio-oils. The results here reported demonstrate the remarkable catalytic properties of the Ga-MFI nanosponge zeolite as it exhibits a suitable combination of accessibility and acidity.

Experimental Section

This section is provided through the Supporting Information file.

Results and discussion

Properties of MFI-nSP and MFI-nSH

MFI zeolite samples were synthesized in the form of aluminosilicate (Al) and galliosilicate (Ga), both in the nanosponge and nanosheet form. Nanosheet form is composed of the thin multilamellar layers arranged as “house-of-cards”.¹⁴ In contrast, the nanosponge material is composed of the domains connected in a disordered way to form sponge-like mesoporous particles.^{30,31} The powder XRD patterns (Figure 1a, d) of Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponges (nSP), and Al- and Ga-MFI nanosheet (nSH) zeolites exhibited the characteristic Bragg reflections that correspond to the typical MFI zeolite topology.³² The diffraction lines in both nanosponge and nanosheet MFI are relatively broad because of the small crystalline domains. Thus, only the $h0l$ lines can be identified due to the lack of the long-range order in the crystallographic b -axis direction.^{33–35} These results were in a good agreement with previous works³¹ and the results of STEM measurements (*vide infra*).

Textural properties of the Al- and Ga-MFI-nSP and Al- and Ga-MFI-nSH samples were investigated by argon physisorption (Figure 1c, d, e, f). According to the IUPAC definition,^{36,37} all samples show a type I isotherm at low relative pressures (p/p_0), while at intermediate-high pressures, type IV isotherms are observed. The significant increase in the adsorbed amount at high p/p_0 values is due to the filling of the mesopores or interparticle void volumes.^{38,39} While both nSP zeolites present quite similar isotherms, some differences are observed in the case of the nSH

samples. In this way, the contribution of the adsorption at intermediate relative pressures ($p/p_0 = 0.4-0.8$) is higher in the case of the Ga-containing material, denoting it presents a lower degree of stacking of the nanosheets than the Al-MFI-nSH zeolite. As reported in Table 1, Al- and Ga-MFI-nanosponges exhibit a large external/mesopore surface area and a high mesopore volume than the nanosheet materials. For the latter, the Ga-MFI-nSH sample possesses an external/mesopore surface area significantly higher than the Al-containing one. The pore size distributions (Figure 1e, f) were determined using NLDFT model assuming a cylindrical pore geometry. The sharp peak at 0.56 nm is assigned to the micropores in the MFI-type zeolite, and the second peak in the range of 5-8 nm in both Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponges and Al- and Ga-MFI nanosheet samples denotes the presence of mesopores.

Figure 1. XRD patterns, Ar adsorption-desorption isotherms and NLDFT pore size distribution of Al-MFI-nSP and Ga-MFI-nSP (a, c, e) and, Al-MFI-nSH and Ga-MFI-nSH (b, d, f) samples, respectively.

Table 1. Textural properties of the zeolite samples determined from Argon (-186 °C) adsorption-desorption isotherms.

Sample	S_{BET} (m ² /g)	$S_{ext/meso}$ (m ² /g)	V_{micro} (cm ³ /g)	V_{meso} (cm ³ /g)	V_{tot} (cm ³ /g)
Al-MFI-nSP	438	309	0.04	0.44	0.51
Ga-MFI-nSP	464	308	0.05	0.43	0.51
Al-MFI-nSH	386	165	0.09	0.19	0.30
Ga-MFI-nSH	425	238	0.07	0.31	0.39

S_{BET} : BET surface area; $S_{ext/meso}$: External/mesopore surface area.

V_{micro} : Micropore volume; V_{meso} : Mesopore volume; V_{tot} : Total pore volume (P/P₀ = 0.99).

ICP-MS elemental analysis of materials indicated that Al-MFI-nSP and Ga-MFI-nSP had similar silicon to heteroelement ratios, i.e. Si/Al of 38 and Si/Ga of 40, respectively. Nanosheet MFI samples have a higher content of Al or Ga comparing to nanosponge counterparts, nevertheless heteroelement incorporation was again similar for Al and Ga (Si/Al of 23 and Si/Ga of 25, respectively). This led us to the conclusion that the conditions and procedure employed for the synthesis of MFI nanosheets lead to a higher incorporation of both Al and Ga in comparison with those of nanosponge architecture.

The coordination of the heteroatoms in the zeolite samples was investigated by ⁷¹Ga and ²⁷Al MAS NMR (Figure S1). Regarding to the Al-containing samples, both materials present a well-defined peak, with chemical shift at about 50 ppm, which corresponds with Al tetrahedrally coordinated atoms incorporated into the zeolite framework. Likewise, in both cases the presence of octahedrally coordinated Al, originated from extra-framework species, is also denoted (peak at c.a. 0 ppm). The share of the latter is significantly lower for the Al-MFI-nSP sample (2.2 %) in comparison with the material in the form of nanosheets (9.7 %). Similarly, for both Ga-containing

samples, the resonance spectrum indicates that the majority of the gallium is incorporated into tetrahedral positions (chemical shift at 150 ppm²⁹), whereas the contribution of octahedral Ga species (signal at 0 ppm) is so small that cannot be quantified in a reliable way.

Crystal morphology of prepared materials was investigated by SEM imaging (Figure S2). Both nanosponge and nanosheet MFI zeolites are composed of polycrystalline aggregates which differ in size. Nanosponge Al-MFI-nSP (Figure S2a, b) and Ga-MFI-nSP (Figure S2c, d) particles are of approximately 0.5 μm in diameter, while nanosheet materials (Al-MFI-nSH (Figure S2e, f), and Ga-MFI-nSH (Figure S2g, h)) comprise of bigger agglomerates (of approx. 20 μm and 5 μm in size for Al-MFI-nSH and Ga-MFI-nSH, respectively).

Details of the architecture of both textural types of materials were investigated by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM, Figure 2). The crystalline MFI nanosponge domains (Figure 2a, b, c, d) are built of lamellar crystals, which are randomly interconnected to each other in a disordered manner forming sponge-like mesoporous particles in agreement with the results of Kim et al.³¹ On the other hand, nanosheet multilamellar crystals of Al-MFI-nSH and Ga-MFI-nSH (Figure 2e, f, and g, h, respectively) are composed of 2–10 nm thick lamellae with visibly higher aspect ratio. Individual lamellar crystals are bigger and stacked in more organized way in respect to each other than in case of nanosponge materials. Nevertheless, nanosheet crystals are partially packed, which creates interparticle spaces between individual lamellae, which is reflected in the mesopore volume of nanosheet material.

Figure 2. STEM images of Al-MFI-nSP (a, b), Ga-MFI-nSP (c, d), Al-MFI-nSH (e, f), and Ga-MFI-nSH (g, h) samples.

To provide a detailed information about the type, amount, and strength of the acid sites of the calcined samples, FTIR spectroscopy of adsorbed pyridine was used, the results obtained being reported in Table 2 and Figure S3. At 150 °C, the populations of Brønsted acid sites in Al-MFI-nSP and Al-MFI-nSH are higher than those in the corresponding Ga-counterparts, which agrees

with previous investigation.⁴⁰ When increasing the pyridine desorption temperature, the differences in the concentration of the Brønsted (C_B) and Lewis (C_L) acid sites between the samples are narrowed, showing that they exhibit relatively close populations of the strongest acid centers. On the other hand, for both Al and Ga zeolites, the C_B/C_L ratio is higher in the case of nanosponge samples in comparison with nanosheet ones. These results evidence that the nature of the acidity depends strongly not only on the type of metals but also on the nanolayers arrangement. However, in the case of the Brønsted acid sites located on the external/mesopore surface, which have been quantified by FTIR/DTBPy measurements, their concentration is controlled mainly by the metal type. Al-containing samples exhibit higher concentrations of Brønsted acid sites accessible for DTBPy than the Ga-MFI materials (Table 2).

Table 2. Acid properties of the zeolite samples from FTIR/Py and FTIR/DTBPy at 150 °C.

Sample	C_B^a (mmol/g)	C_L^b (mmol/g)	C_B/C_L	$C_{B-ext/meso}^c$ (mmol/g)
Al-MFI-nSP	0.199	0.091	2.19	0.08
Ga-MFI-nSP	0.149	0.158	0.94	0.05
Al-MFI-nSH	0.169	0.117	1.44	0.08
Ga-MFI-nSH	0.130	0.187	0.70	0.05

C_B , C_L , $C_{B-ext/meso}$: Brønsted, Lewis and external/mesopore Brønsted acid sites concentration.

LDPE catalytic pyrolysis

The zeolite samples were firstly tested in the catalytic pyrolysis of low-density polyethylene (LDPE). This reaction is of a practical interest as a possible route for the valorization of the increasing amounts of waste plastics. In addition, the bulky polymer molecules and the necessity of strong acid sites for promoting the C-C cracking reactions make this reaction a useful test for

assessing both the accessibility and the acidic features of the catalysts. The reaction system employed in this work (semi-batch stirred reactor) involves the direct contact between the melted polymer and the zeolite catalyst in powder form. The selected temperature for the LDPE pyrolysis tests (350 °C) ensures a negligible contribution of thermal pyrolysis at least in terms of volatiles generation, as confirmed by the blank experiment performed in the absence of catalyst. In addition, under these conditions, amorphous materials (like Al-MCM-41) and conventional ZSM-5 samples are little active due to its weak acidity and low share of external surface area, respectively⁴¹⁻⁴³.

Table S1 shows the product mass yields of gas, liquid, and solid/non reacted fractions obtained in the catalytic pyrolysis of LDPE with the Al and Ga-containing nano-sheets and nano-sponges materials. The gases consist of C₁-C₄ components (olefins and paraffins with little methane), whereas the liquid is formed mainly by hydrocarbons within the gasoline range (C₅-C₁₀). The superior activity of the Ga-MFI-nSP catalyst is denoted by the low yield of solid residue (16.6 %wt.), consisting mainly of non-degraded plastic, and the high production of liquid hydrocarbons (55.9 %wt.) obtained with this sample. On the contrary, Al-MFI-nSH leads to a quite low liquid production (18.9 %wt.), accompanied with the highest amount of non-reacted LDPE (58.4 %wt.).

In this way, the efficiency of the LDPE pyrolysis reaction system can be quantified through the Reaction Mass Efficiency (RME)⁴⁴ parameter, a mass-based metric employed to evaluate the sustainability of a determined process. This parameter is defined as the percentage of valuable products relative to the mass of reactants. The RME range for the LDPE pyrolysis process considering as valuable products both gas and liquid fractions, is between 41.6% and 84%, for the samples Al-MFI-nSH and Ga-MFI-nSP, respectively. These RME values confirm that the sustainability of the LDPE pyrolysis process can be dramatically enhanced by carefully selecting the properties of the employed catalyst.

The catalytic activity obtained over the different zeolite samples, estimated as the mass of LDPE converted in respect to the weight unit of the catalyst, has been represented in Figure 3a and 3b versus two key catalyst properties: the external/mesopore surface area and the overall acid sites concentration, respectively. As a reference, the results obtained with a micron-size ZSM-5 sample have been also included (see Figure S4 for a summary of its properties), showing a small activity in spite of its high acidity that denotes the great effect of accessibility issues. Thus, a clear relationship can be observed in Figure 3.a. between the LDPE cracking activity and the external/mesopore surface area of the zeolite catalyst. In contrast, the influence of the overall concentration of acid sites (Brønsted + Lewis acid centers) is quite less evident (Figure 3b). Thus, the largest catalytic activity is obtained over the MFI samples in the form of nano-sponges, which can be assigned mainly to their remarkable accessibility coming from their high external/mesopore surface area. Nevertheless, some acidity effects may arise from the different nature of the acid sites when comparing Al- and Ga-containing samples (see Table 2). Thus, in spite of the Ga-MFI materials exhibiting significantly less Brønsted (both overall and external) acid sites concentrations than the Al-MFI counterparts, their LDPE cracking activity is close to that of the latter. This result suggests that the high Lewis acidity, present in both Ga-MFI samples, contributes also to the LDPE pyrolysis process, probably by promoting hydride abstraction reactions.

Figure 3. LDPE catalytic pyrolysis over Al- and Ga-MFI Nanosponge (nSP) and nanosheet (nSH) samples. Catalytic activity referred to: external surface area (S_{ext}) (a), and Brønsted + Lewis acid sites concentration ($C_B + C_L$) (b). Selectivity towards gaseous and liquid fractions (c). A micron-size ZSM-5 sample has been also included as reference.

In terms of product distribution, a higher selectivity towards liquid-range hydrocarbons is achieved over the Ga-containing catalysts (Figure 3c), whereas both Al-MFI zeolites in the form of nanosheets and nano-sponges generate more gaseous hydrocarbons. In particular, a $C_1 - C_4$ selectivity

of c.a. 55 % is reached over the Al-MFI-nSH sample, which can be also a consequence of its lower accessibility compared with the other materials since it may hinder the occurrence of secondary reactions leading to liquid products. In this way, the small activity exhibited by the reference ZSM-5 sample is reflected in its negligible production of liquid range hydrocarbons. On the other hand, dehydrogenation reactions followed by the oligomerization/cyclization/aromatization (OCA) pathway seem to be preferentially promoted over both Ga-MFI zeolites. Thus, as shown in Figure S5, the Ga-MFI-nSP sample exhibits a superior selectivity towards ring-containing products (naphthenes and aromatic hydrocarbons), which are formed through the OCA route.

Oak wood catalytic pyrolysis

The performance of the zeolites under study in lignocellulose catalytic pyrolysis (oak wood) has been investigated using an ex-situ reaction system provided with a catalytic fixed bed. The thermal decomposition of the lignocellulosic feedstock took place in the upper part of the reactor, where the carbonaceous solid (char) so formed was accumulated, thus avoiding the direct contact between biomass/char and the catalysts. Accordingly, the char yield was very similar for all the experiments varying in the range 26 – 28 wt.%, referred to the raw biomass. Since the vapors produced in the thermal zone contain a high share of oligomers and relatively bulky species, derived from the decomposition of the holocellulose and lignin biopolymers, their further catalytic upgrading is expected to be strongly affected not only by the zeolite acidity but also by its accessibility. On the other hand, in addition to C-C cracking reactions like in the case of the LDPE conversion, deoxygenation transformations are also pursued during the oak catalytic pyrolysis to afford the production of a bio-oil* fraction (bio-oil in a water-free basis) with low oxygen content. This fact represents an important difference between both catalytic tests.

As shown in Figure 4a, the different fractions obtained from oak catalytic pyrolysis are produced with some variations depending on the employed catalyst. In overall, both Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponge zeolites exhibited a higher activity than the nanosheet materials. This is evidenced by the enhanced formation of both gases and water over the MFI-nSP samples, which in turn is associated with a decrease in the yield of the organic liquid fraction (bio-oil*). The negative impact on the bio-oil* yield of the different catalysts is compensated by the improvement of its composition due to the decrease in its oxygen content regarding that of the thermal bio-oil* (c.a. 40 wt.%). The most pronounced effect is observed with the MFI-nSP samples and, in particular, over the Ga-MFI-nSP catalyst since the bio-oil* so obtained shows a low oxygen content (c.a. 17 wt.%), which indicates the superior activity of this material for the upgrading of the organic liquid phase.

In the gaseous stream (Figure 4b), the main components were CO and CO₂, whose formation is also favored when using the nanosponge zeolite samples. The enhanced production of H₂O, CO and CO₂ denotes high deoxygenation activity of the MFI-nSP materials through dehydration, decarbonylation and decarboxylation reactions, respectively.

Figure 4. Oak wood thermal and catalytic pyrolysis: fractions mass yields and oxygen content in bio-oil* (being GO, gaseous olefins, and GP, gaseous paraffins) (a) and gases mass yields (b).

The relationship between the mass/energy yield of the bio-oil* fraction and its oxygen content is illustrated in Figure 5, showing that the Ga-containing zeolites exhibit a better performance than

the corresponding aluminosilicate zeolites. In particular, the Ga-MFI-nSP sample affords a highly deoxygenated bio-oil* with a relatively large yield (about 30 % in energy terms). As a reference, the results obtained with the micron-size ZSM-5 sample (see properties of this material in Figure S4) have been also included in these graphs, showing it presents a low activity for bio-oil* conversion and upgrading in spite of possessing a high acid sites concentration. This result can be assigned to the low external surface area of this material, confirming the relevance of the zeolite accessibility in oak catalytic pyrolysis. Nevertheless, the above commented results demonstrate that the nature of the active sites plays also a significant role in the catalytic activity during the bio-oil upgrading process. This difference can be rationalized taking into account that, compared with the LDPE cracking, catalytic pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass involves many more chemical transformations and species (with a diversity of oxygenated components), with a high prevalence of deoxygenation reactions that are, however, absent in the conversion of polyolefins.

Figure 5. Oak wood catalytic pyrolysis over Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponge and nanosheet samples: oxygen concentration versus bio-oi* mass (a) and energy (b) yield, respectively (a micron-size ZSM-5 sample is also included as reference).

Figure 6 provides the composition of the bio-oil* fractions according to the different compounds' families (AC, carboxylic acids; LO, light oxygenates; FUR, furans; O-AR, oxygenated aromatics; MAH, monoaromatic hydrocarbons; PAH, polyaromatic hydrocarbons; SUG, sugars). The main components correspond to oxygenated aromatics (mainly phenol and cresol) and aromatic hydrocarbons (e.g. toluene and xylene). Whereas the former can be directly linked to the decomposition of lignin, different routes have been proposed to explain the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons during lignocellulose catalytic pyrolysis over zeolites. The most important ones are the transformation of sugars via furans through the Diels-Alder condensation with gaseous olefins and the already commented OCA (oligomerization/cyclization/aromatization) pathway. Figure 6a shows that the formation of monoaromatic hydrocarbons (MAH) is strongly enhanced with the nanosponge zeolite catalysts, the highest concentration by far being reached with the Ga-MFI-nSP zeolite (24.4 wt.%). Although this effect is accompanied by an important increase in the content of polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), the overall MAH/PAH ratio remains high. These results agree with the low oxygen content of the bio-oil* obtained with the Ga-containing nanosponge zeolite, confirming the high deoxygenation and aromatization activities of this catalyst, which can be assigned to both its remarkable accessibility and balanced Brønsted/Lewis acidity.

Figure 6. Oak wood thermal and catalytic pyrolysis: mass concentration of compounds families (AC, carboxylic acids; LO, light oxygenates; FUR, furans; O-AR, oxygenated aromatics; MAH, monoaromatic hydrocarbons; PAH, polyaromatic hydrocarbons; SUG, sugars) (a), mass concentration of GC-MS detected compounds by GC-MS (b) and aromatic hydrocarbons carbon yield (c) in bio-oil*.

The effect of the zeolite accessibility in lignocellulose catalytic pyrolysis is also evidenced when assessing the share of overall bio-oil* mass detected in the GC-MS analyses. From Figure 6b, it is clear that the proportion of GC-MS detected components significantly increased when using the nanosponge zeolites as catalysts, reaching values up to about 65 wt.%, which is much higher than the value corresponding to the thermal bio-oil* (about 36 wt.%). This finding can be explained by

the enhanced conversion of heavy/oligomeric species present in the bio-oil* into lighter components over the external/mesopore surface of the zeolitic catalysts.

Finally, it must be highlighted that the changes observed in the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons are denoted not only regarding the bio-oil* composition but also in terms of yield. As shown in Figure 6c, the Ga-MFI-nSP sample leads to the highest carbon yield of aromatic hydrocarbons, reaching a noticeable 7.4 % referred to the raw biomass.

Conclusions

Although possessing the same zeolitic structure, MFI samples in the form of nanosponges (nSP) and nanosheets (nSH) present, not only different textural properties, but they also show sharp variations in terms of acidic features. MFI-nSP materials exhibit a higher ratio of Brønsted/Lewis acid sites concentration in comparison with MFI-nSH samples. In addition, the share of Lewis acid sites is significantly superior for the materials with Ga in the framework instead of Al atoms.

In the LDPE catalytic pyrolysis, both Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponge samples show a superior activity than the zeolites in the form of nanosheets, which can be assigned to their higher accessibility. Likewise, Ga-MFI samples display a remarkable LDPE cracking activity, suggesting that, in addition to the important role of the Brønsted acidity, the high Lewis acid site concentration present in these materials contributes also to the LDPE pyrolysis process through hydride abstraction from paraffins, i.e. promoting dehydrogenation reactions. Subsequently, the so formed olefins are transformed through the oligomerization/cyclization/aromatization (OCA) pathway, explaining the higher selectivity towards liquid-range hydrocarbons, rich in cyclic and aromatic components, which is observed over the Ga-containing catalysts in comparison with the Al-MFI zeolites.

In the case of oak wood catalytic pyrolysis, both Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponge zeolites exhibit also a higher activity than the materials in the form of nanosheets, which is evidenced by the enhanced production of both gases and water and the associated decrease in the yield of the organic liquid fraction (bio-oil*). This negative impact on the bio-oil* yield is compensated by the strong decrease in its oxygen content. The most pronounced effects are observed over Ga-MFI-nSP that leads to a highly upgraded bio-oil* having the lowest oxygen content, a high share of GC-MS detected components and the largest yield of aromatic hydrocarbons. Compared to LDPE cracking, the catalytic activity in oak pyrolysis is not only determined by the zeolite accessibility but it is also significantly affected by the nature of the acid sites, which can be related with the huge number of chemical transformations and species (involving a diversity of oxygenated components) present during the bio-oil upgrading process. In this way, the outstanding catalytic properties of the Ga-MFI-nSP can be assigned to the combination in this material of a high accessibility and a balanced Brønsted/Lewis acidity that favors both the conversion of bulky substrates and the preferential occurrence of dehydrogenation reactions to produce light olefins that are subsequently transformed into aromatic hydrocarbons through both Diels-Alder condensation with furans and the oligomerization/cyclization/aromatization pathway.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The following file are available free of charge.

Experimental Section. Figure S1. ^{27}Al MAS NMR (a) and ^{71}Ga MAS NMR (b) measurements of the calcined samples. Figure S2. SEM images of Al-MFI-nSP (a, b), Ga-MFI-nSP (c,d), Al-MFI-nSH (e,f), and Ga-MFI-nSH (g,h) samples. Figure S3. Concentration of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites as a function of the pyridine evacuation temperature: Al-MFI-nSP (a), Ga-MFI-nSP (b), Al-MFI-nSH (c), Ga-MFI-nSH (d). Figure S4. Basic characterization and properties of the micron-size ZSM-5 sample: X-ray diffraction (a), TEM micrographs (b, and c), BET surface area, external surface area (t-plot), and microporous and total pore volume from the Ar (-186 °C) isotherm (d), Brønsted (C_B) and Lewis (C_L) acid sites concentration at 150 °C from the FTIR/Py measurements (e), and weak and strong acid concentration determined by TPD-NH₃ (f) (intervals between 100 °C and 240 °C, and 240 °C and 550 °C, respectively). Figure S5. LDPE catalytic cracking over Al- and Ga-MFI nanosponge (nSP) and nanosheet (nSH) samples: product distribution (selectivity) according to hydrocarbon types ($C_1 - C_{14}$). Table S1. Product mass yields of gas, liquid, and solid/non reacted fractions obtained in the catalytic pyrolysis of LDPE over the zeolite catalysts. References. (DOCX).

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

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ABBREVIATIONS

AC, carboxylic acids; BAS, Brønsted acid sites; DTBPy, 2,3-di-tert-butylpyridine; FTIR, Fourier-transform infrared; FUR, furans; GO, gaseous olefins; GP, gaseous paraffins; ICP-MS, inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry; LAS, Lewis acid sites; LDPE, low density polyethylene; LO, light oxygenates; MAH, monoaromatic hydrocarbons; NLDFT, non-local density functional theory; nSH, nanosheet; nSP, nanosponge; O-AR, oxygenated aromatics; OCA, oligomerization, cyclization and aromatization; PAH, polyaromatic hydrocarbons; Py, pyridine; RME, Reaction Mass Efficiency; STEM, scanning transmission electronic microscopy; SUG, sugars.

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SYNOPSIS

Enhanced production of valuable chemicals from plastics and lignocellulose residues by catalytic pyrolysis over Al/Ga MFI zeolites exhibiting suitable accessibility/acidity combination.

